

PbS-based quantum dot solar cells with engineered π -conjugated polymers achieve 13% efficiency

*Muhibullah Al Mubarak[†], Febrian Tri Adhi Wibowo[†], Havid Aqoma[†], Narra Vamsi Krishna^{†‡},
Wooseop Lee[⊥], Du Yeol Ryu[⊥], Shinuk Cho^{§,*}, In Hwan Jung^{‡,*} and Sung-Yeon Jang^{†*}*

[†]School of Energy and Chemical Engineering, Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology (UNIST), 50 UNIST-gil, Ulsan 44919, Republic of Korea

[‡]Department of Chemistry, Kookmin University, 77 Jeongneung-ro, Seongbuk-gu, Seoul 136-702, Republic of Korea

[⊥]Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, 50 Yonsei-ro, Seodaemun-gu, Yonsei University, Seoul 03722, Republic of Korea

[§]Department of Physics and EHRSC, University of Ulsan, Ulsan 44610, Republic of Korea

Corresponding Author

* E-mail: syjang@unist.ac.kr; ihjung@kookmin.ac.kr; sucho@ulsan.ac.kr

ABSTRACT

While hole extraction is crucial for the external quantum efficiency of conventional n-i-p colloidal quantum dot (CQD) solar cells (CQDSCs), sulfur-passivated p-type CQDs (pCQDs) have been the best hole-transport material (HTM) thus far. In this work, we developed organic π -conjugated polymers (π -CPs) that can achieve substantially improved HTM performance compared with conventional pCQDs. A weakly electron-withdrawing triisopropylsilylethynyl (TIPS) group was employed with a weak donor moiety, benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']-dithiophene (BDT), in the push-pull structured π -CPs to optimize the optoelectronic properties of the HTM. The CQDSCs using TIPS-containing π -CPs achieved a substantially higher PCE (13.03%) than those previously reported using pCQD (11.33%) or π -CPs (11.25%) owing to the improved charge collection efficiency near the photoactive CQD layer/HTM interface. To the best of our knowledge, our CQDSCs using TIPS-based π -CPs achieved the highest reported PCE among SSE-free CQDSCs.

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Colloidal quantum dot (CQD)-based solar cell (CQDSC) devices are good candidates for low-cost power generators, owing to their narrow bandgap and low-temperature processability.^{1, 2} In the last decade, the power conversion efficiency (PCE) of CQDSCs has considerably improved to ~13%.³⁻¹² The long-term air- and photo-stability of CQDSCs have also improved significantly, which is promising for potential commercial applications.^{8, 11, 13} Recently, n-type CQD ink (nCQD-ink) has emerged as the state-of-the-art photoactive layer. It has a low trap-state density and can be prepared as films without using solid-state ligand-exchange (SSE) or layer-by-layer (LbL) deposition. However, sulfur-passivated p-type CQDs (pCQDs), fabricated using SSE, have been the dominant hole-transport materials (HTMs).^{3, 12, 14, 15} Moreover, from the processing viewpoint, the extra SSE step adds another complication for conventional high-throughput processes.¹⁶ Strategies for manufacturing high-efficiency SSE-free CQDSCs that may be critical for their commercialization are still needed.^{8, 11, 13, 17-20}

Recently, SSE-free CQDSCs have been achieved by replacing pCQD-based HTMs with organic p-type materials.²¹⁻²⁶ Although the PCEs of CQDSCs with organic HTMs are still inferior to those of conventional pCQD-based devices, the potential of tuning the chemical structures of organic HTMs promises further improvement.²¹⁻²⁶ The energy levels, optical absorption, and charge transport property have been critical factors that determine the performance of organic HTMs.²⁴ Among organic HTMs, π -conjugated polymers (π -CPs) with a structure of alternating electron-rich (donor, D) and electron-deficient (acceptor, A) moieties have demonstrated tunable optoelectronic properties by the judicious selection of the D and A units.^{24, 27} While the A moiety determines the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) level, the choice of the D moiety majorly influences the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) level of the resulting π -CPs.²⁸

In our earlier studies, the benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']-dithiophene (BDT) moiety was employed as a D unit because its weak electron-donating character lowers the HOMO level of organic π -CPs while offering adequate hole mobility.^{24, 27} The SSE-free CQDSC with PBDTPD-HT demonstrated a PCE of 11.53%, and this is comparable to that of devices with conventional pCQD HTMs.^{17, 27} In those studies, the optoelectronic properties that determined the performance of π -CP HTMs were discussed. The development of π -CP HTMs with more favorable optoelectronic properties by tuning their chemical structures might boost the PCE of SSE-free CQDSCs.

In this work, we developed an SSE-free CQDSC with a PCE of 13.03% using newly developed organic π -CP HTMs. Triisopropylsilylethynyl (TIPS)-derivatized BDT was adopted as the D unit, while two different A units, 1,3-bis(4-hexylthiophen-2-yl)-5-octyl-4H-thieno[3,4-c]pyrrole-4,6(5H)-dione (TPD) and 1,3-bis(2-ethylhexyl)-5,7-bis(4-hexylthiophen-2-yl)-4H,8H-benzo[1,2-c:4,5-c']dithiophene-4,8-dione (BDD), were used for the π -CP HTMs (TIPS-TPD and TIPS-BDD). The substitution of the TIPS moiety on the BDT group effectively lowered the HOMO levels of the π -CP HTMs due to its electron-withdrawing character.²⁹⁻³¹ Furthermore, the bandgap of π -CP HTMs became wider, and this minimized the parasitic optical absorption (i.e., optimized the charge generation) in CQDSCs. To fairly evaluate the performance of TIPS-containing HTMs (TIPS-HTMs), π -CP HTMs containing a conventional 2-ethylhexyl-thiophene (EHT) substituent (EHT-HTMs)³² were also prepared as their counterparts. The SSE-free CQDSC devices were fabricated using iodide-capped nCQD-ink as the photoactive layer. The devices with TIPS-HTMs demonstrated improved charge generation and extraction compared with those with EHT-HTMs owing to the low parasitic absorption and enhanced internal electric field. The device using TIPS-TPD achieved a substantially higher PCE (13.03%) than the device using EHT-TPD

(11.25%). To the best of our knowledge, the PCE of our TIPS-TPD device has the best performance among the reported SSE-free CQDSCs.

Figure 1. (a) Chemical structure of π -CP HTMs. (b) HOMO and LUMO levels of TIPS-TPD and EHT-TPD from DFT calculations.

The chemical structures of TIPS-HTMs are depicted in Figure 1a, and the synthetic schemes are shown in Figure S1 and S2. The structure and molecular weight of the TIPS-HTMs were confirmed using ^1H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and gel permeation chromatography (GPC) (Figure S3–S6). The electron-withdrawing character of TIPS effectively decreases the electron density of the BDT core, while its bulkiness offers sufficient solubility to the resulting π -CPs. The A moiety (TPD and BDD) is well known as the weak electron-withdrawing moiety that determines the bandgap and energy levels of the π -CPs. The TIPS-HTMs exhibited blue-shifted absorption compared with the EHT-HTMs due to weaker intermolecular charge transfer (Figure 2a).

The energy levels of the TIPS-HTMs were determined by an ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS) analysis. The Fermi and HOMO levels were determined from the onset of the valence band edges region and the secondary electron cut-off (Figure S7). The LUMO levels were determined based on these HOMO levels, and the optical bandgap (E_g) energies determined from the absorption spectra of the HTM films (Figure 2a).^{11, 33} The energy levels of the TIPS-HTMs that correspond to the UPS analysis are shown in Figure 2b. All π -CP HTMs used in this study exhibited suitable HOMO levels for hole transfer from nCQD-ink active layers, while their LUMO levels were sufficiently high to block electron transfer.^{11, 21, 24, 34} The incorporation of the TIPS group on the BDT unit lowered the HOMO and Fermi levels of the TIPS-HTMs compared with those of the EHT-HTMs counterparts. The HOMO (and Fermi) level of TIPS-TPD and TIPS-BDD were -5.33 (-4.46) eV and -5.34 (-4.36) eV, respectively, while those of the EHT-TPD and EHT-BDD were -5.03 (-4.41) eV and -5.01 (-4.40) eV, respectively. The lower-lying energy levels of the TIPS-TPD compared with the EHT-TPD are also shown in the results of the density functional theory (DFT) calculations (Figure 1b).

Figure 2. (a) UV-vis spectra of π -CP-HTM films, (b) energy levels of nCQD and π -CP-HTMs and (d) the structure of CQDSC device.

The CQDSC devices using π -CP HTMs were fabricated with a ITO/ZnO/nCQD-ink/HTM/MoO_x/Ag structure (Figure 2c). The ZnO electron-transport layer (ETL) (~40-nm-thick) was prepared by in-situ sol-gel conversion on ITO that was deposited on glass substrates.^{7, 35} The nCQD-ink was synthesized by the phase-transfer exchange of oleate-capped CQDs with PbI₂ following our previous report.⁷ The thickness of the light-absorbing nCQD-ink active layer that was deposited by a direct single-step spin-coating method, was ~370 nm. The π -CP HTM layers were spin-coated on the nCQD-ink layers. Finally, the MoO_x/Ag (8 nm/120 nm) anode was thermally deposited at a reduced pressure (<10⁻⁶ torr). A thin MoO_x layer was used to prevent pin-hole formation and to provide more efficient hole injection/extraction.³⁶⁻³⁸ For the device using a conventional pCQD HTM, 1,2-ethanedithiol (EDT) was used for the post-SSE treatment. Au was used as the anode for the device with a pCQD HTM to obtain optimal performance.^{7, 11}

Figure 3. J - V characteristics under AM 1.5G one sun illumination (a-b) and IPCE spectra (c-d) of CQDSCs; (a) TIPS-TPD and EHT-TPD devices, (b) TIPS-BDD and EHT-BDD devices, (c) TIPS-TPD and EHT-TPD devices, (d) TIPS-BDD and EHT-BDD devices. The insets of (a) and (b) show the statistical distribution of device PCEs (20 devices for each).

Table 1. Summary of device performance.

Devices	PCE (%)	V_{OC} (V)	J_{SC} (mA/cm ²)	FF	J_{SC} EQE (mA/cm ²)
TIPS-TPD	13.03 (12.62±0.21)	0.66 (0.65±0.01)	28.80 (28.34±0.37)	0.69 (0.69±0.01)	27.97
EHT-TPD	11.25 (10.86±0.27)	0.62 (0.61±0.02)	28.02 (27.76±0.47)	0.65 (0.65±0.01)	27.18
TIPS-BDD	12.54 (12.03±0.28)	0.66 (0.65±0.01)	28.88 (28.33±0.28)	0.66 (0.66±0.01)	28.03
EHT-BDD	10.03 (9.67±0.25)	0.59 (0.59±0.01)	27.67 (26.61±0.85)	0.62 (0.62±0.02)	26.74

The current density–voltage (J - V) characteristics of the CQDSC devices using π -CP HTMs were measured under simulated AM 1.5G one sun illumination (Figure 3a and 3b), and the results are summarized in Table 1. The PCE of the CQDSCs with TIPS-TPD was optimized at a thickness of ~10 nm (Figure S8), indicating that the film was sufficiently uniform at that thickness. The devices using TIPS-HTMs demonstrated significantly improved PCEs compared with those using EHT-HTMs. The TIPS-TPD device achieved the highest PCE of 13.03% (open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) of 0.66 V, short-circuit current density (J_{SC}) of 28.80 mA cm⁻², and fill factor (FF) of 0.69), while the EHT-TPD device exhibited a PCE of 11.25 % (V_{OC} of 0.62 V, J_{SC} of 28.02 mA cm⁻², and FF of 0.65). The J_{SC} values calculated from the external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra (Figure 3c and 3d) showed good agreement with the trend of the J_{SC} values from the J - V curves,

with a mismatch of $\sim 3\%$ (Table 1). The device performance statistics from 20 devices of each type confirmed the reproducibility of these results (inset of Figure 3a and 3b and Table 1). Notably, the TIPS-TPD device achieved a substantially higher PCE than the device using the current state-of-the-art HTM, pCQD, (11.33 %) (Figure S9). The 13.03% PCE of our TIPS-TPD device is the highest among reported SSE-free CQDSCs.^{17, 26, 27} The environmental stability of the unencapsulated devices containing π -CP HTMs was measured following the ISOS-D-1 protocol (in the dark, $\approx 25^\circ\text{C}$, 40% humidity, in air).³⁹ The PCE retention of the TIPS-TPD and EHT-TPD devices was 90% and 87% from their initial PCE after 1440 h, respectively (Figure S10). This result indicates that the well-covered hydrophobic polymer HTMs effectively block moisture and oxygen.⁴⁰⁻⁴²

Figure 4. Optical distribution in (a) TIPS-TPD and (b) EHT-TPD devices, (c) profiles of charge generation rate of EHT-TPD (left) and TIPS-TPD (right) devices.

To understand the origin of the improved performance of the CQDSCs with TIPS-HTMs, we first investigated the charge generation rate (G) in the devices. The optical distributions in the devices were simulated using the transfer matrix formalism (TMF). For the optical simulations, the refractive index (n) and extinction coefficient (k) of nCQD-ink, EHT-TPD, and TIPS-TPD were measured using spectroscopic ellipsometry (Figure S11). The optical constants of ITO, ZnO,

MoO_x, and Ag were obtained from the literature.⁴³⁻⁴⁵ Figure 4a and 4b show the fraction of optical absorption within the CQDSCs using TIPS-TPD and EHT-TPD, respectively, over the entire wavelength range. These fractions were obtained by the integration of the optical electric field profiles with respect to the wavelengths at various positions in the devices, as shown in Figure 4c. While the absorptions of the other layers of the devices (ITO, ZnO, nCQD, MoO_x and Ag) are nearly identical, the absorptions of the π -CP HTM layers were different (yellow color in Figure 4a and 4b). The TIPS-TPD showed less absorption (i.e., lower parasitic absorption) than EHT-TPD in the device. The G profiles were altered, especially near the Ag electrode; thus, the EQE spectra of the two devices showed different patterns (Figure 3c). The simulated EQE spectra, where the internal quantum efficiency (IQE) was assumed to be 100%, also confirmed the difference (Figure S12). The difference in G was reflected in the J_{SC} of the devices. The estimated J_{SC} value of TIPS-TPD, obtained from the integration of the EQE spectra, was higher than that of the EHT-TPD device (Table S1).

The CQDSCs with TIPS-HTMs exhibited substantially improved PCE, V_{OC} , and FF compared with those with EHT-HTMs. To elucidate the origins of the improved performance in devices containing TIPS-HTMs, the charge transport/recombination properties of the devices were investigated. Figure 5 shows the results from transient photovoltage/photocurrent (TPV/TPC) spectroscopy and an intensity-modulated photocurrent/photovoltage spectroscopy (IMPS/IMVS) analysis. The charge recombination lifetimes (τ_{rec}) were obtained from the TPV analysis by fitting the photovoltage decay curves with a mono-exponential decay function (Figure 5a). The TIPS-TPD device showed a ~20% longer τ_{rec} (116 μ s) than the EHT-TPD device (94 μ s). The charge transport time (τ_{tr}) of the TIPS-TPD device, determined from the TPC analysis, was much shorter (1.05 μ s) than that of the EHT-TPD device (1.18 μ s) (Figure 5b). The improved charge extraction

of the TIPS-TPD device was also confirmed by IMVS and IMPS analysis (Figure 5c and 5d). The τ_{rec} values of the TIPS-TPD and EHT-TPD devices, determined from IMVS, were 29.8 and 25.1 μs , while the τ_{tr} values were 0.40 and 0.46 μs , respectively (Table S2).

Figure 5. Charge extraction property analysis of CQDSCs; (a) TPV (b) TPC analysis results, and (c) IMVS and (d) IMPS analysis results.

Charge transfer at the nCQD/HTM interface was also investigated using fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM).⁴⁶ The samples were excited at 470 nm using a laser, and the distribution of time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) was constructed as images consisting of 200×200 pixels. The obtained photoluminescence decays were fitted with a double exponential decay function, where the faster decay is related to the extraction of the photocarrier.⁴⁷ The TIPS-

TPD device showed a shorter decay lifetime (0.45 ns) than the EHT-TPD device (0.57 ns), indicating improved interfacial charge transfer at the nCQD/HTM interface (Figure 6a and S13). As shown in Figure 6a, the distribution of the shorter decay lifetime was uniform over a wide area ($80 \mu\text{m} \times 80 \mu\text{m}$) of the nCQD/TIPS-TPD sample. This result confirms that the TIPS-TPD uniformly covered the nCQD-ink layer with a thickness of 10 nm.

Figure 6. (a) FLIM images of nCQD/HTM; nCQD/TIPS-TPD film (left) and nCQD/EHT-TPD film (right). (b) Mott-Schottky plots of TIPS-TPD and EHT-TPD devices.

The Mott–Schottky analysis of the capacitance–voltage (C_p – V) measurements revealed that the TIPS-TPD device has a higher built-in voltage (V_{bi}) (0.47 V) than the EHT-TPD device (0.42 V) (Figure 6b). The increased internal electric field in TIPS-TPD was beneficial for boosting V_{OC} and facilitating charge extraction.^{14, 48, 49} The hole mobilities (μ_h) of TIPS-TPD and EHT-TPD were also evaluated by space-charge-limited current (SCLC) analysis of hole-only devices (ITO/PEDOT:PSS/HTM/Au). The Mott–Gurney model was used to calculate μ_h via linear fitting of the SCLC trap-free regime (Figure S14).⁵⁰ The μ_h of TIPS-TPD was $8.23 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and this is lower than that of EHT-TPD ($4.53 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$). These results reveal that the improved charge extraction of the TIPS-TPD device mainly originates from the faster hole transfer

and reduced charge recombination at the nCQD/HTM interfaces rather than the hole transport within the HTM layers. Moreover, this result confirms that the hole mobility of π -CP HTMs is not a crucial factor in determining the device PCE because they are considerably thinner than conventional pCQD HTMs (~ 60 nm).^{24,27} Conversely, the V_{bi} and interfacial charge recombination play more critical roles in determining the PCE of CQDSCs. The trend in device performance was confirmed by the device simulation results using the solar cell capacitance simulator (SCAPS) method (Figure S15). The TIPS-TPD device showed higher simulated V_{OC} , J_{SC} , and FF compared with the EHT-TPD device, indicating the improved interfacial charge extraction of TIPS-TPD overpowered its lower hole mobility.

Figure 7. IQE spectra of (a) TIPS-TPD device and (b) EHT-TPD device obtained at different applied voltages (V_{app}). The $IQE(V_{app}) = EQE(V_{app})/EQE(V_{-2V})$.

To elucidate more details of the charge extraction properties, the bias-dependent IQE spectra, in which the measured EQE curves were divided by the EQE at high reverse bias (-2 V), were plotted.¹⁵ Under a high reverse bias (< -2 V), the active layer is fully depleted; thus, the

maximum EQE is assumed, and this is nearly equivalent to the absorption in the active layer.^[15] It is known that all the photogenerated charges are collected in the fully depleted active layer.^[15] When the voltage for the maximum power point (V_{MPP}) was applied, the depletion region narrows, and the EQE and IQE are reduced due to the recombination of photogenerated carriers.^{15, 51} As shown in Figure 7, the IQE of the TIPS-TPD device in the longer wavelength region (600–1100 nm) was higher than that of the EHT-TPD device under the short-circuit condition and V_{MPP} . This result reveals that lower energy photons are more efficiently collected near the nCQD-ink/TIPS-TPD interface at near open-circuit conditions than at the nCQD-ink/EHT-TPD interface, and this is beneficial for V_{OC} and FF.

In summary, We developed PbS-based, SSE-free CQDSCs with a record-high PCE of 13.03% by improving interfacial charge extraction using newly synthesized TIPS-containing π -CP HTMs. The wider bandgap and suppressed energy levels of TIPS-HTMs, compared with the conventional EHT-HTMs, originate from the electron-withdrawing character of the TIPS moiety, which reduces parasitic absorption and charge recombination in CQDSCs. The interfacial charge transfer at the nCQD/TIPS-HTM interface was uniformly efficient over a large area, even with a TIPS-HTM thickness of only ~10 nm. The PCEs of the devices using TIPS-HTMs were substantially higher those of devices using EHT-HTMs and conventional pCQD HTMs (11.33%). Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, the PCE of our TIPS-TPD device (13.03%) has the best performance among the reported SSE-free CQDSCs.

Experimental Methods

Synthesis of TIPS-TPD polymer: ((2,6-bis(trimethylstannyl)benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene-4,8-diyl)bis(ethyne-2,1-diyl))bis(triisopropylsilane) (263 mg, 0.30 mmol), 1,3-bis(5-bromo-4-

hexylthiophen-2-yl)-5-octyl-4H-thieno[3,4-c]pyrrole-4,6(5H)-dione (227 mg, 0.30 mmol), Pd₂(dba)₃ (9 mg, 0.01 mmol) and P(o-tol)₃ (10 mg, 0.03 mmol) were added to a two-neck round-bottom flask. The mixture was degassed for 30 min, and anhydrous toluene (94.5 mL) was subsequently added to the flask under nitrogen protection. The solution was stirred at 115 °C for 24 h under a nitrogen atmosphere. Then, the reactant was cooled down to room temperature, and the polymer was precipitated into methanol (100 mL). The polymer was collected by filtration and further purified by Soxhlet using acetone, hexane, and chloroform as the eluent. After filtering with Celite and removing the solvent by rotary evaporator, the polymer was precipitated again in methanol (100 mL) and obtained as a dark purple solid with a yield of ~90%. Mn = 36.3 kDa; PDI = 3.30. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 7.54 (br, aromatic protons), 7.02 (br, aromatic protons), 2.94 (br, aliphatic protons), 2.38 (br, aliphatic protons), 2.20 (br, aliphatic protons), 1.58–1.57 (br, aliphatic protons), 1.38–1.29 (br, aliphatic protons), 0.91 (br, aliphatic protons).

Synthesis of TIPS-BDD polymer: On the basis of the procedure described above, the TIPS-BDD was prepared using ((2,6-bis(trimethylstannyl)benzo[1,2-b:4,5-b']dithiophene-4,8-diyl)bis(ethyne-2,1-diyl))bis(triisopropylsilane) (263 mg, 0.30 mmol) and 1,3-bis(5-bromo-4-hexylthiophen-2-yl)-5,7-bis(2-ethylhexyl)-4H,8H-benzo[1,2-c:4,5-c']dithiophene-4,8-dione (281 mg, 0.3 mmol). Yield = ~95%. Mn = 36.4 kDa; PDI = 2.35. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 7.74 (br, aromatic protons), 7.54 (br, aromatic protons), 7.02 (br, aromatic protons), 2.97 (br, aliphatic protons), 2.38 (br, aliphatic protons), 2.20 (br, aliphatic protons), 1.81 (br, aliphatic protons) 1.58–1.38 (br, aliphatic protons), 1.34–1.28 (br, aliphatic protons), 1.00–0.88 (br, aliphatic protons).

Device fabrication: Indium tin oxide (ITO) was cleaned by sonication in acetone and isopropyl alcohol for 20 min and dried at 120 °C overnight. The ZnO sol gel for the ETL was prepared by following a previously reported method.^{7, 35} ZnO was spin-coated onto the ITO substrate at 1000

rpm for 20 s. The n-type CQD inks were prepared using a method similar to the one reported using PbI_2 as the ligand.⁷ The nCQD-ink as-prepared powder was diluted with 5% butylamine in dimethylformamide as a solvent ($\sim 700 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$). The CQD ink solution was spin-coated onto the ZnO film at 600 rpm for 80 s to achieve $\sim 370 \text{ nm}$ of thickness and heated at $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 min. The polymer HTMs were prepared by dissolving them in chlorobenzene at various concentrations and depositing them by spin-coating on nCQD-ink films at 1000 rpm for 60 s. Finally, MoO_x (8 nm) and Ag (120 nm) as the anode was thermally evaporated under low pressures ($< 10^{-6}$ torr).

Device characterizations: The current density-voltage characteristics were recorded using a Keithley 2401 source unit under simulated AM 1.5G solar radiation at 100 mW cm^{-2} (Newport). The light intensity was calibrated using a monosilicon photodetector certified at the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL). A black mask with a defined open active area of 5.18 mm^2 (the area of the aperture was confirmed by an accredited institute, Newport) was used to measure all devices.⁵² The EQE spectra were attained using monochromated light with a 100 Hz chopper frequency (Newport, IQE-300), which was calibrated with a silicon/germanium photodiode. The TPV/TPC measurements were taken using 0.1 mW cm^{-2} as the bias light intensity. A Xe lamp (300 W, Newport) was used as a bias light source, and a nanosecond laser (10 Hz, NT342A, EKSPLA) was used as a small-perturbation light source. IMPS and IMVS were carried out using an impedance analyzer (IVIUM Tech., IviumStat). The DC and AC components of the illumination source were provided by a red emission light-emitting diode (LED) ($\lambda = 660 \text{ nm}$) with 50% modulation depth of the AC component superimposed on the DC light. The mean transit time (τ_t) and recombination time (τ_r) of photogenerated charges were obtained from the minimum frequency in the Nyquist plot of the IMVS and IMPS results by $\tau_{r,t} = (2\pi f_{\min})^{-1}$. Capacitance–

voltage measurements were performed using an impedance analyzer (IVIUM Tech., IviumStat) with an AC signal set to a 5000 Hz frequency and 50 mV amplitude under a CP-RP model.

Characterizations: UV-vis spectra were acquired using an S-3100 (Scinco Co. Ltd). ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AscendTM-400 spectrometer, with tetramethylsilane as an internal reference. The number and weight average molecular weights of the polymers were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) with a Waters 2690 Associates liquid chromatography instrument equipped with a Waters 2414 differential refractometer. Chloroform was used as the eluent, and polystyrene was used as the standard. The hole mobility was obtained from the SCLC method with an ITO/PEDOT:PSS/HTM/Au device structure. UPS was performed using an AXIS-NOVA (Kratos) system with the samples coated on gold substrates under the ambient atmosphere.

Optical and device simulation: Solar Cell Capacitance Simulator (SCAPS) software (version 3.3.07) was used to simulate the CQDSCs performance parameter under AM 1.5G 100 mW cm^{-2} illumination with respect to the HOMO level and hole mobility. The parameters used in this simulation were obtained from a previous report, with slight modification, and are summarized in Table S3 and S4. The optical modelling of CQDSCs was performed using the transfer matrix formalism (TMF) method implemented in MATLAB code developed by McGehee group. The optical constants of the nQD, TIPS-TPD and EHT-TPD films were measured using spectroscopic ellipsometry (VASE, J.A. Woollam Co. Inc.), while the optical constants of the ITO, ZnO, MoO_x , and Ag films were obtained from a previous report.

Supporting Information. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at

<http://pubs.acs.org>.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*E-mail: syjang@unist.ac.kr; ihjung@kookmin.ac.kr; sucho@ulsan.ac.kr

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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